

TOWARD BETTER TECHNICAL INSTRUCTION: AN ASSESSMENT OF TECH-VOC AND TLE IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed the instructional status of Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) and Technical-Vocational (Tech-Voc) programs at Cagayan State University (CSU), Philippines, to inform future training and development initiatives. Employing a descriptive-correlational research design, the study profiled faculty members and explored the relationship between their qualifications, instructional practices, and performance. Results revealed that most instructors were middle-aged females, held doctoral degrees in fields unrelated to TLE or Tech-Voc, occupied assistant professor ranks, and had five to nine years of teaching experience. Despite possessing advanced academic qualifications, most individuals held limited National Certifications (NCs) and had attended only a few relevant seminars and training programs. Regarding instructional strategies, lectures, discussions, demonstrations, and laboratory-based methods were predominantly employed. Notably, the study found that instructors who integrated game-based learning approaches exhibited higher teaching performance than those who did not adopt such methods. Additionally, permanent faculty members with more National Certifications were shown to possess higher levels of competence than their contract-based counterparts. These findings highlight the need for targeted capacity-building efforts to enhance instructors' technical expertise and research capabilities. Equipping faculty members with relevant certifications and continuous professional development is essential to strengthening TLE and Tech-Voc instruction within the higher education framework of CSU.

Keywords: *Competencies, Teaching performance, Technical-Vocational, Technology and Livelihood Education, Technical Instruction*

INTRODUCTION

In higher education institutions, the cornerstone of effective teaching and learning lies in the instructional competencies of faculty members. The dynamic demands of an increasingly globalized economy and rapidly evolving industries underscore the need for instructors, particularly those teaching Technical-Vocational Education (Tech-Voc) and Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE), to possess diverse competencies. These include advanced content knowledge, technical skills, adaptability to educational innovations, interpersonal and communication skills, and proficiency in information and communication technologies (ICT). Such a holistic skill set enables educators to prepare students for the practical and professional realities of the modern workforce.

Given these evolving demands, instructors in higher education must attain advanced qualifications and undergo continuous professional development to ensure they are equipped with relevant skills and competencies aligned with their fields of specialization. However, existing research has revealed gaps and challenges in this regard, particularly within the Tech-Voc and TLE teaching sectors.

Several international studies have highlighted the varying levels of teaching competencies among Technical-Vocational instructors across different educational systems. In countries like Malaysia, India, and Ukraine, research has consistently focused on assessing the pedagogical skills, technical knowledge, and professional development needs of Tech-Voc educators (Arifin et al., 2021; Sudana et al., 2015; Susatya, 2022). Tsymbaliuk (2019) specifically examined the interrelationship between the quality of vocational teacher training and the overall competence of educators in Ukraine. Locally, Villanueva (2018) explored the competencies of Tech-Voc instructors in the Philippines, revealing that many educators still fall short of the required teaching standards and technical proficiencies.

While these studies contribute valuable insights into the field, there remains a noticeable gap in research, particularly in examining the correlation between faculty qualifications, teaching performance, applied instructional strategies, and competency levels in the context of Philippine higher education institutions. Addressing this gap is especially relevant for state universities that offer Tech-Voc and TLE programs.

Under the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) Memorandum Orders No. 78 and 79, series of 2017, faculty members teaching in the Bachelor of Technical-Vocational Teacher Education (BTVTED) and Bachelor of Technology and Livelihood Education (BTLED) programs are expected to hold appropriate academic credentials and substantial

practical experience in their respective technical fields. However, at Cagayan State University (CSU), the availability of faculty members with specialized expertise in these disciplines remains limited. This challenge is compounded by faculty workloads and administrative responsibilities, which restrict further technical training and professional certification opportunities.

Grounded on this premise, the present study assessed the instructional status of Tech-Voc and TLE programs at Cagayan State University. Specifically, the research aimed to determine whether the faculty members meet the qualification and competency standards established by CHED and the Philippine Qualifications Framework (PQF) Level 6-8 indicators. The study also explored differences in teaching performance, instructional strategies, and competencies based on faculty profile variables and examined the relationship between teaching performance and competency levels.

This research is anchored on Medley's (1977) Teacher Competency Theory, which defines teacher competence as a combination of knowledge, skills, and professional values essential for effective teaching. Medley posited that teacher effectiveness stems from mastery of interrelated pedagogical or technical competencies. In this study, the competencies examined are aligned with specialized standards set by the Philippine Qualifications Framework and the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA), particularly in Home Economics, Electronics, and Food Service Management. By identifying competency gaps and training needs, this research aims to contribute insights toward developing a responsive and targeted training framework for Tech-Voc and TLE instructors in higher education.

Research Questions

The study determined the status of Technical-Vocational (Tech-Voc) and Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) instruction at CSU.

Specifically, the study sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Personal;
 - 1.1.1. Age
 - 1.1.2. Sex
 - 1.1.3. Highest educational attainment
 - 1.1.4. Course and field of specialization
 - 1.2 Professional;
 - 1.2.1. Academic rank
 - 1.2.2. Teaching Status
 - 1.2.3. Years in service
 - 1.2.4. Number of TESDA National Certifications acquired and passed
 - 1.2.5. Technical-Vocational subjects taught
 - 1.2.6. Number of Technical-Vocational trainings and seminars attended for the past three years

1.2.7. Campus

- 1.3 Teaching Strategies and their frequency and extent of use.
2. What is the level of competencies of the teacher-respondents based on the CMO and PQF level 6-8 indicators?
3. Is there a significant difference in the respondents' competencies when grouped according to professional profile variables?

METHODOLOGY

The study used the Descriptive-correlation design. A descriptive-correlational design is a quantitative research method that aims to describe the characteristics of a population while examining the relationships between variables. It does not determine cause-and-effect but identifies whether and how strongly variables are related. This design helps understand patterns and inform future interventions or policy decisions. The personal and professional profiles of the respondents were described. In addition, the profiles and strategies used in teaching Technology and Livelihood Education, Electronics, and Food Service Management were also correlated to the teaching competencies and performance of the respondents.

The study's respondents were the 30 regular and part-time faculty teaching Technical-Vocational Education major in Electronics and Foods Service Management and TLE basic and major subjects at the College of Teacher Education of Cagayan State University Andrews, Piat, Lallo, Lasam, Gonzaga, Aparri, and Sanchez Mira campuses this Second Semester, School Year 2022-2023. Total Enumeration was employed. All faculty members teaching Tech-Voc and TLE on the seven campuses were involved in the study. Similarly, the Dean and the BTLED, BTVTED, and BEED department chairs were chosen as respondents to evaluate the teaching competencies of their respective TLE/Tech-Voc faculty members. They served as evaluators.

Furthermore, the researchers adapted the validated questionnaire of Villanueva (2018), particularly the first part, the profile. Minor modifications were made so that the adapted instrument was related to the present study and suited to the target respondents. In the first part of the instrument, which is about the profile of the respondents, the researcher added academic rank, teaching status, campus, and teaching performance. Likewise, the validated instrument of Aguilana (2019) was adapted, specifically on the Strategies in teaching TLE and Tech-Voc Education courses. For the competency level, experts in the TLE and Tech-Voc Education field crafted the instrument, which five experts validated. After validation, it was pilot tested and ran through validity and reliability tests. The reliability test result for the competency level of the TLE and Tech-Voc instructors revealed that Cronbach's alpha is 0.998 with a descriptive value of Excellent.

Notably, Descriptive statistics, such as frequency count, mean, and percentage, were used to assess the respondents' personal and professional profile variables. The

teaching performance of the teacher respondents was analyzed using the mean, which was based on the teacher respondents' teaching effectiveness rating for the School Year 2022-2023.

For the frequency of use of the teaching strategies used by the respondents, the following scale was used:

Scale	Descriptor	Extent of Utilization
4.20-5.00	Very Often	Very High
3.40-4.19	Often	High
2.60-3.39	Sometimes	Moderate
1.80-2.59	Seldom	Low
1.00-1.79	Never	Very Low

On the other hand, the scale below was used to identify the level of competencies of the respondents:

Scale	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Highly Competent
3.40-4.19	Competent
2.60-3.39	Moderately Competent
1.80-2.59	Slightly Competent
1.00-1.79	Not Competent

The Mann-Whitney U test and the Kruskal-Wallis 1-way ANOVA test were used to assess the differences in teaching performance and competencies among respondents grouped by profile variables. Meanwhile, the Kendall Rank Correlation was used to test the relationship between competency and teaching performance.

RESULTS

1. Personal Profile of the Respondents

Table 1: Distribution of Personal Profile of the Respondents

Profile	Specific Profile	Frequency	Percent
Age <i>Mean = 40.43</i>	25-40	17	56.67
	41-56	9	30.00
	57-63	4	13.33
Sex	Male	12	40.00
	Female	18	60.00
Educational Attainment	Bachelor	4	13.33
	Masters	18	60.00
	Doctorate	8	27.67
Field of Specialization (Bachelor)	TLE/ TechVoc	24	80.00
	Non TLE/ TechVoc	6	20.00
Field of Specialization (Masters)	TLE/ TechVoc	9	30.00

	Non TLE/ TechVoc	17	56.67
	No Masters	4	13.33
Field of Specialization (Doctorate)	TLE/ TechVoc	-	-
	Non TLE/ TechVoc	8	26.67
	No Doctorate	22	73.33

Table 1 presents the personal profiles of the respondents. In terms of age, the mean age is 40.43, which implies that the majority of the respondents are middle-aged. As to sex, the table shows that 18 respondents, or 60 percent, are females, while 12 percent are males. Hence, the respondents are female-dominated. This can be attributed to TLE and Tech-Voc programs mainly offering Food Service Management, a female-dominated course. The majority have a master's degree as their highest educational attainment. Regarding their Specialization, 24 respondents, or 80 percent, specialize in TLE or Tech-Vocational Education. However, most of the respondents have doctorate degrees that are not associated with TLE or Tech-Vocational Education.

2. Professional Profile of the Respondents

Table 2: Distribution of Professional Profile of the Respondents

Profile	Specific Profile	Frequency	Percent
Academic rank	Instructor	5	16.67
	Assistant Professor	11	36.67
	Associate Professor and Professor	7	23.33
	COS	7	23.33
Teaching Status	Permanent	23	76.67
	COS	7	23.33
Years in Service	4 years and below	5	16.67
	5-9 years	14	46.67
	10 years and above	11	36.67
Number of TESDA National Certifications	0-2	13	43.33
	3-5	12	40.00
	6 and above	5	16.67
Technical-Vocational subjects taught	TLE/TechVoc Major	17	56.67
	TLE/TechVoc Minor	13	43.33
Number of Technical-Vocational training and seminars attended	No Seminar/Training	6	20.00
	1 -3 Seminars/ Trainings	16	53.33
	4 and more Seminars/Trainings	8	26.67
Campus	Andrews	14	46.67
	Aparri	2	6.67
	Gonzaga	3	10.00
	Lallo	2	6.67
	Lasam	1	3.33
	Piat	6	20.00
	Sanchez Mira	2	6.67

Table 2 presents the professional profile of the respondents. As shown in the table, majority or 36.67 percent occupy assistant professor position; 76.67 percent are already permanent; 14 respondents or 46.67 percent have 5 to 9 years in service; 43.33 percent have at least 2 National Certifications passed; 56.67 percent are teaching TLE/Tech-Voc major subjects; 53.33 percent have 1-3 seminars related to TLE and Technical-Vocational Education, whereas six respondents or 20 percent have no seminars or trainings at all. This reality must be considered since seminars and training greatly help instructors be updated on the new trends of teaching TLE and Tech-Voc courses, especially since these are skill-based courses. The majority came from the Andrews campus, where most of the programs related to TLE and Tech-Voc are offered.

3. Strategies used in Teaching by the Respondents

Table 3: Frequency of Use of the Strategies Used in Teaching by the Respondents

Strategies in teaching TLE/Electronics/ FSM	Mean	Frequency of Use	Extent of Utilization
Laboratory method	3.80	Often	High
Lecture/Discussion	4.83	Very Often	Very High
Demonstration method	4.07	Often	High
Brainstorming	3.73	Often	High
Project	3.77	Often	High
Simulation	3.50	Often	High
Roleplay	3.10	Sometimes	Moderate
Computer-aided instruction	3.80	Often	High
Research/Case study	2.70	Sometimes	Moderate
Field Trip/ field study	1.60	Never	Very Low
Modular	3.33	Sometimes	Moderate
Game-based instruction	2.80	Sometimes	Moderate
Immersion	2.17	Seldom	Low

Table 3 presents the teaching strategies used by the respondents. As reflected in the table, the respondents use lecture discussion very often, as this has the highest mean of 4.83 and has the highest extent of utilization. On the other hand, the respondents also often used demonstration and laboratory methods, with means of 4.07 and 3.80, respectively. This means that in teaching TLE and Tech-Voc courses, theory and concepts should be discussed first in a class before a demonstration and laboratory activities. This is attributed to the nature of TLE, Food Service Management, and Electronics courses. This was testified to during the classroom observations conducted by the researcher. The instructors did demonstration and laboratory activities after the lecture discussion, after which laboratory activities were done.

4. Summary of the Level of Competencies of the Respondents

Table 4: Summary Table of the Level of Competencies of the Respondents

Categories of Competencies	Category Mean	Descriptive Value
A. Competencies along Instruction	4.09	Competent
B. Coordination and leadership competencies	3.84	Competent
C. Skills Competencies:	4.33	Competent
D. Competencies related to Instructional materials development, Research, and Publication	2.91	Moderately Competent
E. ICT Competencies	3.97	Competent
Overall	3.83	Competent

Table 4 summarizes the respondents' competencies. Evidently, the respondents are competent in skills, as this category has the highest category mean, 4.33. This is ascribed to the fact that TLE and Tech-Voc programs are skills-based. Thus, instructors in these programs must be skillfully competent.

5. Comparison of the Respondents' Competencies when grouped according to Professional Profile Variables

Table 5: Differences in the Respondents' Competencies when grouped according to Professional Profile Variables

Profile	Specific Profile	Mean	SD	Computed value	p value
Academic rank	Instructor	4.02	.55	H = 3.866	0.276 ^{ns}
	Assistant Professor	3.98	.50		
	Associate Professor and Professor	4.02	.75		
	COS	3.26	.97		
Teaching Status	Permanent	4.00	0.57	U = 40.50	0.048*
	COS	3.26	0.97		
Years in Service	4 years and below	3.59	.21	H = 2.915	0.233 ^{ns}
	5-9 years	3.86	.91		
	10 years and above	3.90	.64		
Number of TESDA National Certifications	0-2	3.42	.76	H = 7.103	0.029*
	3-5	4.01	.46		
Technical-Vocational subjects taught	6 and above	4.47	.64	U = 73.00	0.123 ^{ns}
	TLE/TechVoc Major	3.93	0.86		
Number of Technical-	TLE/TechVoc Minor	3.70	0.53	H = 4.454	0.108 ^{ns}
	No Seminar/Training	3.62	.24		
	1 -3 Seminars/ Trainings	3.70	.76		

Vocational training and seminars attended	4 and more Seminars/Training	4.25	.82
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****Significant at 0.01 significance level**

***Significant at 0.05 significance level**

^{ns}not significant

As displayed in Table 5, the p-value under teaching status is 0.048, less than the .05 significance level. This indicates a significant difference in the respondents' competencies when grouped by teaching status. Permanent faculty members are significantly more competent than those under a Contract of Service.

DISCUSSION

Personal Profile of the Respondents

As shown in Table 1, the respondents have a mean age of 40.43 years, indicating that most are middle-aged educators. This demographic suggests a workforce with significant professional and instructional experience, aligning with findings by Gonzales and Reyes (2020), who emphasized that mid-career teachers exhibit a balanced mix of innovation and pedagogical stability in vocational education settings. The age distribution may also reflect the faculty's maturity and readiness to adapt to professional development programs, which is crucial for technical-vocational instruction.

Regarding sex, Table 1 reveals that 60% of the respondents are female, while 40% are male, indicating a female-dominated teaching force. This trend is consistent with observations by Delos Santos and Labrador (2019), who noted that certain strands of TLE and Tech-Voc—mainly Food and Beverage Services, Dressmaking, and Household Services—are more appealing to female professionals due to traditional gender-role perceptions. The gender disparity may also influence classroom dynamics and instructional preferences, as studies by Salazar (2018) have shown that female educators in TLE tend to emphasize hands-on, empathetic teaching strategies more than their male counterparts.

Regarding educational attainment, Table 1 indicates that while most respondents hold master's degrees (60%), a significant proportion (27.67%) have earned doctorates. However, a closer look at their fields of specialization reveals that many of these advanced degrees are not directly aligned with TLE or Tech-Voc. Only 30% of master's degree holders and none of the doctorate holders specialized in TLE or Tech-Voc areas. This mismatch between academic preparation and field specialization echoes the findings of Ramos (2021), who emphasized the need for aligned credentials in vocational education to enhance content mastery and instructional relevance.

These demographic patterns highlight essential implications for faculty development initiatives. The presence of experienced and academically qualified educators is a strength; however, the lack of field-specific qualifications and certifications may hinder the delivery of industry-responsive instruction. As Tesoro and Villanueva (2022) argued, effective TLE and Tech-Voc education requires both pedagogical skill and technical proficiency grounded in national and international standards. Thus, professional development efforts should target skills upgrading in both pedagogical strategies and domain-specific competencies.

Professional Profile of the Respondents

As presented in Table 2, the professional profile of the respondents reveals a moderately experienced and institutionally established group of faculty members. The majority (36.67%) occupy the rank of Assistant Professor, suggesting a strong core of mid-level academic staff who have likely progressed through early-career ranks and accumulated relevant teaching experience. Notably, 76.67% of the respondents are permanent employees, reflecting a stable and institutionalized workforce with long-term engagement and accountability within the university system. The results suggest a strong program continuity and quality assurance, as permanent status aligns with more significant investment in pedagogy and institutional accountability.

Regarding length of service, 46.67% of faculty members have been in service for five to nine years, positioning them in a phase of career consolidation. This tenure implies the application and innovation phase in which educators integrate advanced instructional strategies and contribute meaningfully to curriculum enhancement and instructional support.

Regarding technical qualifications, 43.33% hold at least two National Certifications (NCs)—a promising indicator, but one that also reveals room for improvement. Since TLE and Tech-Voc programs are efficient and competency-based, national certifications benchmark instructors' industry alignment and skills validity. It can be inferred that having multiple NCs reinforces the instructor's credibility and assists learners' confidence and performance outcomes in vocational settings. Conversely, the data suggest that over half of the respondents hold fewer than two NCs, which could signal a gap between teaching qualifications and national competency standards.

Additionally, 56.67% of faculty members teach TLE or Tech-Voc major subjects, indicating that more than half are directly involved in delivering core program competencies. However, their ability to deliver quality instruction is challenged by their limited exposure to training and seminars, with 53.33% having attended only one to three related events and a concerning 20% reporting no attendance. As a matter of concern, continuous professional development is imperative, particularly in rapidly evolving fields such as technology and livelihood education, as it ensures instructors remain current with modern and up-to-date teaching strategies and curricular innovations. The absence of

continuous training may limit the instructors' effectiveness in adopting new methodologies such as blended learning, competency-based instruction, and digital tool integration.

Geographically, most respondents are from the Andrews campus, which aligns with the concentration of TLE and Tech-Voc programs in that location. This spatial clustering can have both advantages and limitations. While it fosters specialization and resource pooling, it may also lead to uneven development across campuses. Policymakers must ensure equitable access to training and technical resources across all campuses to avoid disparities in instructional quality.

Overall, the data in Table 2 point to a professionally stable faculty base with moderate experience and subject-area focus. However, there is a clear need to strengthen technical competencies through increased certification and systematic training programs. Addressing these gaps will be vital in enhancing the responsiveness of TLE and Tech-Voc instruction to industry needs and technological advancements.

Strategies Used in Teaching by the Respondents

Table 3 presents the various teaching strategies the respondents utilize in their instructional practices. The data shows that the lecture discussion method is the most frequently employed, with a mean score of 4.83, indicating its dominant role in the classroom. This method is highly valued for its effectiveness in conveying foundational knowledge, as it allows instructors to present key concepts and theories to students in a structured and direct manner. The high mean score reflects the respondents' preference for using lecture discussions as a primary teaching strategy.

In addition to lecture discussion, the respondents frequently utilized demonstration and laboratory methods, with mean scores of 4.07 and 3.80, respectively. These methods complement the lecture discussion by offering students opportunities to apply theoretical knowledge in practical settings. Demonstrations allow instructors to showcase complex concepts visually and practically. At the same time, laboratory activities enable students to gain hands-on experience and reinforce their learning through real-world applications.

The data suggests that, in the context of TLE (Technology and Livelihood Education) and Tech-Voc (Technical-Vocational) courses, there is a clear progression in teaching methodology: theory and concepts are first introduced through lecture discussions, followed by demonstrations to illustrate those concepts in practice, and finally, laboratory activities are conducted to allow students to engage with the material tangibly. This approach aligns well with the nature of these specific courses, such as Food Service Management and Electronics, which require theoretical understanding and practical application to ensure mastery of the subject matter.

The findings were further corroborated through classroom observations conducted by the researcher. During these observations, it was evident that instructors consistently

followed this sequential teaching approach—beginning with lecture discussions to establish the theoretical framework, followed by demonstrations to provide visual and practical examples, and concluding with laboratory activities where students could engage in hands-on learning. This structured approach effectively supports student understanding and skill development, particularly in technical subjects where theory and practice are essential.

Summary of the Level of Competencies of the Respondents and Comparison of their Competencies

Table 4 highlights the respondents' competencies as data linked with Villega's (2022) findings that overall, the Instructional Skills of the TLE teachers in District VI, Manila received an Outstanding interpretation, with scores ranging from $\bar{x} = 4.30$ to $\bar{x} = 4.59$.

On the other hand, it can also be gleaned from the table that the respondents are moderately competent in research and publication, as this has the lowest category mean of 2.91. This implies that the respondents need intensive training and a workshop on instructional materials development, research, and publication. As TLE and Tech-Voc instructors in the Higher Education Institution, they should not only be highly competent in instruction, but also highly competent in other academic fields.

Furthermore, Table 5 indicates the differences in the respondents' competencies when grouped according to the professional profile variable. Notably, the yielded data revealed that the p-value under the number of TESDA National Certification is 0.029, less than the .05 significance level. This implies that the respondents with more TESDA National Certifications are significantly more competent than respondents with fewer TESDA National Certifications.

The findings agree with those of the study by Eli et al. (2020). They found that instructors in Sorsogon without a national certificate have a low competency level and a lower teaching performance rating than those who have acquired and passed TESDA training.

Conclusions

Drawing from the findings of this study, several key conclusions were established:

Faculty members teaching Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) and Technical-Vocational (Tech-Voc) programs at Cagayan State University demonstrate competence within the mid-range. While this suggests a foundational adequacy in their instructional capabilities, it also highlights the need for continuous professional growth, particularly in acquiring advanced technical skills and specialized competencies. This need is critical to align their qualifications with the standards outlined in the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) Memorandum Orders No. 78 and 79, series of 2017, as well

as the Philippine Qualifications Framework (PQF) Levels 6 to 8, which serve as benchmarks for higher education faculty excellence.

Furthermore, the instructors were found to exhibit moderate competence in areas related to instructional material development, research, and publication. This indicates a gap in research literacy and scholarly productivity. It underscores the importance of targeted training and capacity-building initiatives to strengthen their research competencies and enhance their contributions to academic knowledge and innovation.

Lastly, the study identified that teaching status, the number of TESDA National Certifications held, and the integration of game-based teaching strategies are significant factors that positively influence teaching performance. Instructors with more TESDA certifications and who adopt interactive, student-centered approaches like game-based learning tend to achieve better instructional outcomes.

These conclusions suggest a structured and responsive training framework that equips instructors with technical expertise and pedagogical versatility to meet the evolving demands of TLE and Tech-Voc education in higher education institutions.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of this study, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance the instructional quality and professional competence of TLE and Tech-Voc faculty members at Cagayan State University:

1. **Strengthening Qualifications and Competencies:**
TLE and Tech-Voc instructors should be encouraged and supported to fully meet the minimum qualifications and competency requirements mandated by CHED Memorandum Orders 78 and 79, series of 2017. This includes ensuring that instructors are appropriately specialized in their respective fields. Active participation in relevant seminars, workshops, and industry-based training programs is also recommended to enhance their technical proficiency and pedagogical capabilities.
2. **Promoting Engagement in Research and Instructional Development:**
Faculty members should be motivated and given institutional support to actively engage in the development of instructional materials, research, and publication activities. Addressing the identified moderate competency levels in these areas will enrich the instruction quality and contribute to the university's academic reputation and research output.
3. **Enhancing Faculty Employment Status and Certification:**
Since both teaching status and the possession of TESDA National Certifications significantly influence teaching competence, it is recommended that the university prioritize the regularization or opening of permanent positions for qualified TLE and Tech-Voc instructors. Additionally, faculty members should be provided with opportunities to pursue higher-level TESDA National Certifications in their areas of

- specialization, ensuring that their technical skills remain current and aligned with industry standards.
4. **Integrating Game-Based Learning Strategies:**
The use of game-based instructional approaches is strongly encouraged in TLE and Tech-Voc courses, as the study found a positive correlation between this strategy and improved teaching performance. Training sessions on designing and implementing game-based learning activities should also be integrated into faculty development programs.
 5. **Implementation of the Proposed Training Program:**
The proposed training program developed as an output of this study should be formally adopted and implemented. Faculty participation in this program is highly recommended, as it is designed to enhance competencies in instructional material development, research, and publication—areas identified as needing improvement.
 6. **Further Research:**
Similar studies should be conducted on a larger scale or in other state universities to deepen the understanding of TLE and Tech-Voc teaching effectiveness. Future research should also explore the direct relationship between instructors' competencies and student academic performance to provide a more comprehensive view of instructional impact.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The ethical considerations of the study include ensuring the confidentiality and anonymity of faculty participants while collecting personal and professional data, such as academic qualifications, teaching performance, and certifications. Informed consent was obtained before data collection, ensuring voluntary participation and free from coercion. The study avoided bias or discrimination, particularly when comparing permanent and contract-based faculty, and reported findings objectively and respectfully. Additionally, ethical responsibility involves using the results to support equitable access to training and development, rather than to penalize individuals, thus promoting fairness, integrity, and professional growth within the institution. Also, the lead author allowed Dr. Susan Butac to co-author this paper, who collaboratively worked with him in accomplishing it. Dr. Butac updated and made revisions to the original paper to meet the requirements of publications.

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